

Transdisciplinarity

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Background

Research on global societal challenges – climate change, social inequality, public health – increasingly requires interdisciplinary and cross-institutional collaboration between different scientific communities. However, the potential of transdisciplinarity, cross-disciplinary collaborative projects, knowledge transfer, and data reuse is often not fully realized because content and data must cross methodological and disciplinary boundaries, both technically and intellectually. In what follows, we focus on Digital Objects (DOs), which include a variety of artifacts, such as journal articles, research data, and software. The accessibility and transdisciplinary (re)use of DOs are challenging and require the consideration of a variety of aspects, including both technical-organizational and content-related concerns. Requirements are for example, increasingly interconnected, digitized, and efficient research and data infrastructures; (quality-)criteria from the perspective of the Digital Object provider (documentation and rich metadata); (quality-)criteria from the perspective of transdisciplinary reuse. By this we mean in particular: transdisciplinary Digital Object Management, evaluation of quality by re-users, reintegration of knowledge, and knowledge transfer across the methodological and theoretical paradigms. In this paper, we will focus on two levels: (1) Identifying types of content divergences between source and target discipline and (2) strategies for overcoming these barriers in practice.

Definition of transdisciplinarity

In transdisciplinary physics, transdisciplinarity is commonly referred to as a universal, theoretical *unity of knowledge* principle underlying all sciences providing universal meta-knowledge. In the humanities, social sciences, and economics, transdisciplinarity is closely related to the terms interdisciplinarity or multidisciplinary and often refers to the combination and integration of methods and theories in the sense of integrative and collaborative research. While we do not underestimate the differences in the meaning of the term transdisciplinarity across fields, we strongly recommend an open approach, to identify barriers between different communities and methodologies.

Types of content divergence

If the source discipline and the target context have the same (or similar) understanding related to a DO (vocabulary, terms, concepts, methods, theories, and metadata definitions), conversion of the digital object is not necessary. Provided the semantics are the same, the DO (e.g., vocabulary, labels) can be unambiguously translated (cross-concordances). Otherwise, it is essential to identify and make transparent structural divergences. In the following, cross-disciplinary obstacles are exemplified by four basic types of divergences: (A) divergent semantics, (B) divergent paradigms, (C) divergent subjective perceptions, and (D) fundamental transformation of DO. Please note that the list is not exhaustive.

(A) Divergent semantics

The transdisciplinary use of terms often implies a shift in both the denotation and connotation of definitions. For instance, in behavioral economics, the term *reciprocity* is defined as “a behavioral response to perceived kindness and unkindness.” (Falk & Fischbacher, 2006) thus placing it at the level of individual behavior. In sociology, on the other hand, the term refers to an emergent condition at the societal level: “Reciprocity, the giving of benefits to another in return for benefits received, is a defining feature of social exchange.” (Molm, Schaefer, & Colett, 2007). These discrepancies in the meaning of "reciprocity" imply a different operationalization. Studies thus require different experimental designs to test hypotheses related to the definition of “reciprocity”. Moreover, such differences undermine the validity of meta-study conclusions if they are not considered.

(B) Divergent paradigms

In transdisciplinary collaborative projects, the underlying theories and methodological paradigms may differ. Methodological Individualism constitutes the basis of Coleman's bathtub (Esser, 1999, S.98) as an explanatory scheme for collective action. The starting point is a social fact, for example, the news on the radio that long traffic jams are to be expected next Saturday when school holidays begin. The individual actor perceives this social situation and decides to start her journey on Friday. When she gets in her car and hits the highway on Friday, she is surprised to find that, as an unintended collective outcome of her individual rational decision, others had the same idea and are now all stuck in traffic jams on Friday. However, when social scientists, for example, follow methodological collectivism rather than methodological individualism, this methodological decision allows them to explain collective outcomes through macro theories. In the figure, these macro theories follow the dashed arrow from the social situation directly to the collective outcome. Thus, transdisciplinary research must consider and be transparent to the target context not only regarding the theoretical explanations but the underlying methodological paradigm and assumptions.

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(C) Divergent subjective perception

Citizens, non-experts, and researchers may have a divergent subjective perception of a digital object or (social) situation. Previously unexamined qualitative raw data of the Nagel and Selten experiment (2020) on the beauty-Contest Game illustrate the misleading conclusions that a lack of transparency of subjective perspective can cause. “Beauty-contest” is a game in which participants have to choose, typically, a number in [0,100], the winner being the person whose number is closest to a proportion of the average of all chosen numbers.” (Nagel, Bosch-

Domènech, Sartorra, & Garcia-Montalvo, 1999, p.1), In the experiment of Nagel and Selten (1997), participant No. 24 chooses the number 21,42, which deviates from the game-theoretic solution 0 and could be interpreted as an imperfect decision. But reviewing the subjective perception and reasoning, participant No. 24 started her analysis with the game theoretically correct answer zero and then included her subjective perception of the context to end with the answer (the reasoning would have almost precisely led to the empirically correct result if not for a small assumption error.). Thus, scientists reach wrong conclusions when they fail to consider the subjective perception of a situation.

(D) Fundamental transformation of the DO

Objects (Monsó, 2022) and DOs (e.g., their digital twins) might transform fundamentally. The experiment by Guterstam, Petkova, and Ehrsson (2011) report a perceptual illusion in which a rubber right hand, placed next to the participant's real hand in front of the participant's eyes is perceived as a supernumerary limb of the participant's own body. "[...] one moment the

© GUTERSTAM, A. ET AL., THE ILLUSION OF OWNING A THIRD ARM. IN: PLOS ONE 6, 171208, 2011, FIG. 3 (AUGUST 2011)

participant is looking at a lifeless piece of rubber, and the next moment the rubber hand “comes alive” and becomes part of the participant's perceived body, with the subjective feelings associated with a real limb. This explicit change in the sense of ownership of the rubber hand is what sets this illusion apart from other well-known body illusions“ (Ehrsson, 2020, p. 181). As a result, the rubber arm

treatment needs to be approved by an ethics committee, and any violation of the third arm may be subject to legal prosecution. For transdisciplinary research, the fundamental change of research objects is of utmost relevance. In many fields, objects, situations, and personalities are assumed to be constant and do not change. For instance, machine learning and AI are usually built on the assumption of constant relationships. When algorithms are trained on a rubber arm, they come to wrong predictions once the rubber arm has turned into a body part (and vice versa). For transdisciplinary research, these assumptions must be made transparent to view the output of one discipline of origin from the perspective of another target discipline in a neutral and transparent way.

Strategies for transdisciplinary convergence

To overcome barriers that currently prevent researchers from using a common infrastructure, the following strategies might be helpful: (1) Embed research in transdisciplinary digital object management, using canonical workflow components (CWFR) (Hardisty & Wittenburg, 2020). (2) Use of transdisciplinary metadata to capture as much contextual information as possible and to make methodological paradigms transparent across disciplinary boundaries. (3) (Re)integration of knowledge from the user perspective within the DO. This enhances collaboration in projects and transdisciplinary reuse, moreover, it will improve the quality of data exchange even within a research field.

References

- Betz, D., Biniössek, C., Bianchi, C., Henninger, F., Lauer, T., Wieder, P., Wittenburg, P. & Zünkeler, M. (2022). Canonical Workflow for Experimental Research. *Data Intelligence* 2022, 4(2), 155–172. doi: https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00123
- Ehrsson, H. H. (2020). Multisensory processes in body ownership. In Sathian K., & Ramachandran VS (Eds.), *Multisensory perception: From Laboratory to Clinic*. (pp. 179-200). Academic Press:Elsevier.

- Esser, H. (1999). *Soziologie. Allgemeine Grundlagen*. Frankfurt/New York: Campus Verlag.
- Falk, A., & Fischbacher, U. (2006). A theory of reciprocity. *Games and economic behavior*, 54(2), 293-315.
- Guterstam, A., Petkova, V. I., & Ehrsson, H. H. (2011). The illusion of owning a third arm. *PloS one*, 6(2), e17208.
- Hardisty, A., & Wittenburg, P. (2020). Canonical Workflow Framework for Research (CWFR)-position paper-version 2 December 2020.
- Jeffery, K., Wittenburg, P., Lannom, L., Strawn, G., Biniossek, C., Betz, D., & Bianchi, C. (2021). Not ready for convergence in data infrastructures. *Data Intelligence*, 3(1), 116-135.
- Molm, L. D., Schaefer, D. R., & Collett, J. L. (2007). The value of reciprocity. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 70(2), 199-217.
- Monsó, S. (2022). How to Tell If Animals Can Understand Death. *Erkenntnis*, 87, 117–136. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10670-019-00187-2>
- Nagel, R., Bosch i Domènech, A., Satorra, A., & García Montalvo, J. (1999). One, two,(three), infinity: Newspaper and lab beauty-contest experiments. *Economics and Business Working Paper*, (438).
- Nagel, R.C., & Selten, R. (2020). Dataset E-Mail Decision Reasons for One, Two, (Three), Infinity, ...: Newspaper Beauty-Contest Experiment in Spektrum der Wissenschaft. Retrieved from x-science.org. doi: [10.23663/x2669](https://doi.org/10.23663/x2669)
- Selten, R. & Nagel, R. (November 1997). "1000 DM zu Gewinnen." *Spektrum der Wissenschaft*. p.10.
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., ... & Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3(1), 1-9.